

Mechanism of cold fusion I: Nuclear fusion induced by dislocation annihilation

S. Fukuta

email: luckfield29@gmail.com

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Abstract

Since the historic announcement of cold fusion by Fleischmann and Pons in 1989, numerous experimental results have confirmed nuclear reactions in metals. However, the theoretical framework remains insufficient.

To explain cold fusion in the palladium–deuterium system, I propose a fusion model induced by dislocation annihilation. Huizenga’s three miracles are resolved as the macroscopic force accompanying dislocation annihilation enables quasi-static fusion with atomic-scale confinement to overcome Coulomb repulsion, resulting in selective production of the thermally most stable nucleus, ^4He . Furthermore, the reaction probability and excess heat generation are derived to be proportional to $(D/Pd)^{14}$. The threshold deuterium loading ratio is calculated as 0.85, consistent with McKubre’s law. Thus, this framework provides not only qualitative insight into observed behaviors but also quantitative estimations of cold fusion phenomena.

Finally, Paneth’s experimental results from the 1920s were reevaluated. The amount of helium predicted by my model strongly suggests that Paneth’s experimental observations were indeed correct as the earliest excellent proof for cold fusion.

Keywords: Fleischmann-Pons effect, cold fusion, solid-state nuclear fusion, Huizenga’s three miracles, dislocation, D-D fusion, palladium, helium, deuterium, Hagelstein, McKubre, Miles, Storms, Paneth, dislocation annihilation, reproducibility, LENR

1 Introduction

Since the historic announcement of cold fusion by Fleischmann[1, 2] and Pons on March 23, 1989, numerous investigations have been performed to achieve several revolutionary results. While the cold fusion was investigated in palladium-deuterium systems at first, excess heat in nickel-protium(H) systems was also reported by Notoya[3] and Ohmori[4]. This indicates the

potential for practical applications using low-cost materials like nickel and protium instead of precious ones such as palladium and deuterium, offering overwhelming advantages in resource availability and cost compared to the current thermonuclear fusion using deuterium and tritium. Subsequently, Arakawa[5] confirmed that metal nanoparticles improve reproducibility and excess heat generation. Recently, a cold fusion reactor with four times greater excess heat than the electric input has been achieved at the prototype level[6]. Thus, the cold fusion development has progressed far beyond thermonuclear fusion except for the theoretical frameworks. By the 1990s, heat densities exceeding 3 kW/cm^3 were reported by Fleischmann and Pons[1, 2]. This value is approximately 30 times the typical heat density of 100 W/cm^3 in the core of a WWER (PWR) reactor[7], representing an extremely high value even at that time. Considering that although semiconductor transistors immediately after their invention were less reliable than vacuum tubes, they replaced vacuum tubes through research and improvement, cold fusion should have been given greater emphasis and research. However, in reality, the results of cold fusion research were largely dismissed or ignored[8-14]. These negative conclusions were primarily drawn by those with conflicts of interest regarding cold fusion, and evidently appear unfair.

Although cold fusion had not been officially recognized as a nuclear reaction since its discovery, neutron bursts and the detection of tritium and ^4He , accompanying excess heat, were confirmed[15-30], suggesting that some form of nuclear reaction was occurring in metals. In particular, Miles[21-23], McKubre[26], and Hagelstein[30] experimentally confirmed a strong correlation between ^4He production and excess heat. Thus, through trial and error, numerous experimental proofs of nuclear fusion in metals have been accumulated[31]. Meanwhile, many theories for cold fusion were proposed[16, 32-58]. However, anyone has not yet managed to resolve Huizenga's three miracles[12, 39, 45] and also cannot explain the experimental results comprehensively. Despite sufficient experimental evidence, cold fusion continues to be dismissed as "*pseudoscience*" by the public and mainstream academia simply because it lacks a fully convincing theory[31]. Consequently, despite severe public skepticism, several researchers have persisted, witnessing remarkable phenomena such as large spontaneous excess heat and nuclear reactions[60].

I have devised cold fusion models to develop a nuclear fusion reactor with a practical high power density[61], as it is considered the most efficient way to understand the properties of cold fusion and to resolve the challenges for realizing an ideal fusion reactor within the shortest time frame. The theory can be approximately classified into three types of reactions; fusion induced by dislocation annihilation, neutron chain reactions and the derivative explosive D-D fusion. In this paper, I explain the simplest case — fusion induced by dislocation annihilation — to resolve Huizenga's three miracles[12, 39, 45]. This type of fusion occurs in palladium-deuterium systems and can be explained both qualitatively and quantitatively, including the (D/Pd) loading effect[62-64] in the Fleischmann-Pons effect.

2 Fundamental principles and characteristics of D-D nuclear fusion induced by dislocation-annihilation

In thermonuclear fusion, a D-D fusion reaction is achieved by the dynamic collision of deuterium nuclei[65-67]. The reaction probability is determined by the reaction cross section, relative velocity and energy distribution, and generally proceeds as follows:

The probability difference between the reactions can be explained by the extremely short time of the collisions of two deuterium nuclei. The radius of a deuterium nucleus is 1.3 fm, and the velocity with a kinetic energy of 100 keV is 3.1×10^6 m/s, resulting in a collision time of the order of 10^{-21} seconds. The reactions to ${}^3\text{He}$ and T proceed due to hadronic interactions with the short reaction time of the order of 10^{-22} seconds. On the contrary, the reaction to ${}^4\text{He}$ hardly proceed due to the electromagnetic interactions with longer reaction time of the order of ranging from 10^{-16} to 10^{-12} seconds. Consequently, the reaction cross section to ${}^4\text{He}$ is suppressed by 7-8 orders of magnitude compared to the others.

In the cold fusion in palladium-deuterium systems, however, ${}^4\text{He}$ production dominates over ${}^3\text{He}$ and T productions[19-26]. Moreover, a strong correlation between ${}^4\text{He}$ yield and excess heat was confirmed by Miles[23], McKubre[26] and Hagelstein[30]. Although the domination of ${}^4\text{He}$ production cannot occur in the dynamic nuclei collisions with short reacting time, it can be enabled by static or quasi-static reactions with extremely long reacting time. In static reactions, the equilibrium state becomes dominant. The stabilization energies for T, ${}^3\text{He}$ and ${}^4\text{He}$ are 4.04 MeV, 3.27 MeV, and 23.9 MeV, respectively, leading to a complete transition to ${}^4\text{He}$. Therefore, examining both the Fleischmann-Pons effect[30, 31, 62-64, 68, 69] and the physical properties of palladium, I conclude that the static D-D fusion occurs due to dislocation annihilation.

Figure 1 illustrates the concept of the dislocation-induced fusion. When a dislocation exists, excess deuterium atoms are adsorbed onto the palladium atoms at the dislocation. When the dislocation disappears due to crystalline recovery from external excitation such as heat, two deuterium atoms are forcibly pushed into one hydrogen-storage site. At this point, the two deuterium atoms fuse, resulting in two atomic nuclei existing within the 1s closed-shell electrons. This leads to quasi-static nuclear fusion among nuclei with low kinetic energy. Although the electron screening effect is weak and the reaction probability is low, fusion is achieved by the number of collisions, as the nuclei are confined within the atom. At this time, the reaction time is long enough due to the low velocity of the nuclei, leading to nuclear transmutation into ${}^4\text{He}$ nuclei. This model concretizes the nuclear fusion mechanism proposed by Wada[57] and Arata[58], arising from the dense concentration of deuterium nuclei. Moreover, although nuclear fusion induced by dislocation annihilation has already been proposed by Ooyama[59], fusion by collision of nuclei is assumed and the direction of investigation is different from mine.

This reaction does not produce neutrons. Furthermore, a ^4He is a doubly magic nucleus with two protons and two neutrons, possessing a spherically symmetric configuration and no electric dipole moment. Consequently, electromagnetic radiation is forbidden, resulting in a long photon emission relaxation time. Therefore, the mass deficit energy is considered to be converted into heat via phonons[50] or internal conversion[61]. In the case of internal conversion, which might involve neutron chain reactions, the dislocation-annihilated sites have poor crystallinity, so it is considered that a neutron chain reaction does not necessarily occur. In this limiting state, the excess heat derived from the ^4He yield would match the actual excess heat.

Figure 1: Concept images of D-D fusion induced by annihilation of dislocation; (a) a lattice with dislocation, where excess deuterium atoms are adsorbed on palladium atoms, (b) the lattice after annihilation of dislocation to produce ^4He atoms.

In summary, Huizenga's three miracles[12, 39, 45] are achieved as follows:

- Macroscopic forces accompanying dislocation annihilation overcome Coulomb repulsion, enabling both atomic-scale confinement of deuterium atoms and quasi-static nuclear fusion to produce ^4He selectively.
- No neutron is essentially produced due to the selective ^4He production.
- The symmetry of a ^4He nucleus suppresses photon emission such as X-rays and γ -rays, converting mass deficit energy to heat via alternative pathways.

Furthermore, depending on the situation, it is conceivable that three or more deuterium atoms could be confined in one hydrogen-storage site after dislocation annihilation, potentially explaining the 3–5 MeV neutrons detected by Takahashi[15,16].

From this model, various properties are derived as follows:

- For fusion to succeed by dislocation annihilation, multiple deuterium nuclei in a hydrogen-storage site must not escape via hopping to another hydrogen sites. To prevent the hopping, it requires high (D/Pd) loading, which is observed in the Fleischmann-Pons effect[30, 62-64].
- Since dislocation density depends significantly on manufacturing processes such as rolling and heating, variations in excess heat generation are observed between manufacturers' cathodes[23, 31].
- As cracks result from the growth of the largest dislocations, crack-free conditions are required for high excess heat generation[31, 68, 69].

The subsequent sections will discuss these points in detail.

3 Influence of (D/Pd) loading in Fleischmann-Pons effect

Figure 2 shows the crystal structure of PdD. Palladium has an FCC structure with a lattice constant $a = 3.8907 \text{ \AA}$, while PdD has $a = 4.084 \text{ \AA}$ [70]. The inscribed sphere diameters for the octahedral site (O-site) and tetrahedral site (T-site) are 1.196 \AA and 0.649 \AA , respectively, meaning a hydrogen atom with a diameter of 1.058 \AA occupies the O-site. Furthermore, since the atomic nuclear radii of H and D are extremely small at 1.2 fm and 1.5 fm , respectively, hydrogen can be absorbed into the T-site in an ionized state. Figure 3 shows the isotherms on the pressure-composition plane for the Pd-H system[71]. At 77 K , H/Pd exceeds 1, indicating that the T-sites are occupied by hydrogen. This occurs because the T-site level is higher and more unstable than the O-site level. The activation energies for hydrogen and deuterium to occupy the T-site are estimated to be 64 meV and 73 meV , respectively[72]. Above room temperature, hydrogen occupation of the T-site can be neglected, and hydrogen absorption can be considered solely for the O-site. The excess heat generation of cold fusion in the Pd-D system, which was first termed the Fleischmann-Pons effect by Szpak[73], requires the condition $(D/Pd) \geq 0.85$ [30, 62-64]. Here, we consider the probability P_f of D-D fusion induced by dislocation annihilation. For fusion to occur at the crystal center position shown in Fig. 2(b), two deuterium atoms are required. Furthermore, all twelve adjacent O-sites must be occupied by deuterium atoms to prevent the central deuterium atoms from escaping. Therefore, P_f is given by

$$P_f \propto \left(\frac{D}{Pd} \right)^{14}. \quad (2)$$

Especially, the term of $(D/Pd)^{12}$ represents success probability of the atomic-scale confinement. Figure 4 shows the dependence of P_f on (D/Pd) loading. As clearly shown, even at $(D/Pd) = 0.7$, the value falls down below 0.01, meaning excess heat is not observed unless (D/Pd) is

quite high. In this model, $P_f = 0.1$ can be considered the threshold for excess heat, and the threshold $(D/Pd)_{th}$ is given by

$$\left(\frac{D}{Pd}\right)_{th} = 0.1^{(1/14)} = 0.848 \simeq 0.85. \quad (3)$$

This value is consistent with the thresholds reported by McKubre[30] and Kunimatsu[31]. Furthermore, in Figure 4(b), the region where $0.8 \leq (D/Pd) \leq 1$ can be approximated by an exponential function. Approximating it with an exponential function passing through the points $(D/Pd, P_f) = (1, 1)$ and $(0.7, 0.01)$, P_f is approximately represented by

$$P_f \simeq 2.15443 \times 10^{-7} \cdot \exp \left[15.3057 \cdot \left(\frac{D}{Pd} \right) \right]. \quad (4)$$

(a) Atomic sphere model

(b) Ball-and-stick model

Figure 2: 3D images of a PdD crystal. While pure palladium has an FCC structure, PdD forms a sodium chloride (NaCl)-type lattice.

Well-known experimental data of excess heat dependence on (D/Pd) loading in Pd-D system by McKubre[62] are shown in Figure 5 (a), and the analyzed results in Figure 5 (b). Since Kunimatsu[63] observed excess heat at $(D/Pd) = 0.85$, zero-point correction was applied to Figure 5(a). Specifically, +0.249 W was added to the excess heat value to ensure $(D/Pd)^{14}$ at the lower measurement limit. The exponent of (D/Pd) at the measurement midpoints becomes 18.3, larger than 14.

The wider-ranging experimental data of the (D/Pd) loading dependence of excess heat by McKubre[26] or Hagelstein[30] are shown in Figure 6 (a), and the analyzed results in Figure 6 (b). Measurements were taken up to a higher $(D/Pd) = 0.98$ than in Figure 6. To fit the power law, +0.9 W/cc was added to the measured values, resulting in an exponent of 20.1, which is larger than the values in Figure 6. If the fusion requires preventing protium nuclei from escaping to not only the adjacent O-sites but also the T-sites, the fusion probability

Figure 3: Pressure-composition isotherms (PCIs) of the Pd-H system, reproduced from Lewis[71].

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Dependence of probability of fusion induced by dislocation annihilation on (D/Pd) loading (a) and the enlarged graph (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Dependence of excess heat generation on (D/Pd) loading. (a) Measurement data reproduced from McKubre[62]. A green line at -0.249 W of excess power is new zero level. (b) Analyzed results of data (a). Blue and red points represent the lower limits and median values of the measurement data, respectively.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Dependence of excess heat generation on (D/Pd) loading. (a) Measurement data reproduced from Hagelstein[30]. (b) Analyzed results of black-curve data (a).

may become approximately proportional to $(D/Pd)^{22}$ from $(D/Pd)^{14}$, though a more detailed derivation would be necessary.

Figure 7 shows the measurement results by Mizuno[64]. The vertical axis is a logarithmic scale. Calculating the slope of the exponential function from the slope of the straight line yields $1.795 \cdot \ln(10)/0.437 = 9.41$. The difference from the slope value of 15.35 when approximating $(D/Pd)^{14}$ with an exponential function is large. However, the maximum value of (D/Pd) in Figure 7 is 1.19, exceeding 1, indicates an overestimation. Therefore, correcting the slope using the maximum (D/Pd) value of 0.95 yields an estimated value of $9.41 \times 1.19/0.95 = 11.79$. This corresponds to approximately a exponent of 10.75 in a power-law rule, which is significantly smaller than 14. This is thought to be due to the size effect of palladium cathodes. McKubre[26] and Hagelstein[30] used palladium rods with a diameter of 1 mm, whereas his palladium rod had a diameter of 1 cm[60]. Therefore, it is possible that insufficient deuterium loading occurred across the entire palladium, leading to lower experimental results.

Figure 7: Dependence of excess heat generation on (D/Pd) loading, reproduced from Mizuno[64].

Regarding the (D/Pd) loading effect, experiments by Yamaguchi[18-20] are unique. As deuterium was absorbed in palladium at 400 Torr (0.526 atm) and below 300 °C, the (D/Pd) loading is approximately estimated 0.4, as he reported. This loading was insufficient for excess heat generation. They succeeded in generating excess heat by applying an electric field to migrate deuterium nuclei toward the MnO layer, which blocked deuterium and promoted excess heat by increasing (D/Pd) at the interface. It is also possible that the current-induced electromigration promoted dislocation annihilation.

McKubre[74] listed the following three conditions for excess heat generation:

- Bringing (D/Pd) loading close to 1, mentioned previously.

- Allowing sufficient diffusion time for deuterium to diffuse throughout the entire palladium cathode; for instance, several hundred hours are required for a 3mm diameter cathode to absorb deuterium fully in palladium.
- Another threshold also exists for current density.

Fleischmann[75], Kunimatsu[63], Cravens[68], Storms[69] and others similarly noted the close relationship between excess heat generation and current density. Figure 8 shows the current density versus excess heat generation density plot. Excess heat is nearly proportional to current density. Although excess heat generation is often less than the input power, assuming the current quantum efficiency is 100%, the ideal excess heat gain G_{100} to input power at an applied voltage V is given by

$$G_{100} = \frac{23.8 \times 10^6 \cdot e}{2eV} = \frac{1.19 \times 10^7}{V}, \quad (5)$$

where e is an electron charge. The theoretical electrolysis voltage for water is 1.23 V, and practical V ranges from 1.6 v to 1.9 V for overvoltage. Since V is assumed to be 2 V, G_{100} is estimated to be $\sim 6 \times 10^6$. Thus, it is obvious that the injected deuterium nuclei are scarcely consumed by nuclear reactions. Nevertheless, the current is required because it is reasonable to assume that the current promotes dislocation annihilation via electromigration. Furthermore, "heat after death"[60, 76] refers to spontaneous excess heat generation without power input. Unlike the conventional Fleischmann-Pons effect, it is considered as a chain reaction although it might be also due to the largest dislocation annihilation. I believe a chain reaction occurs due to neutrons generated by the resonant internal conversion of free electrons[61]. The internal conversion energy is 0.78 MeV, and the 0.7 MeV-peak neutrons measured by Mizuno[77] are considered evidence for my theory.

Miles[23] confirmed that the theoretical mass deficit energy predicted from ${}^4\text{He}$ yield agrees with the experimental excess heat. However, as shown in Figure 9, McKubre[26] and Hagelstein[30] obtained a higher value of 30 MeV per ${}^4\text{He}$ atom. However, at low ${}^4\text{He}$ yields, the values appear close to theoretical and reach 30 MeV as excess heat generation increases. This suggests that as the reaction progresses, the aforementioned neutron chain reaction occurs. As the crystallinity in the dislocation-annihilated regions is poor, neutron chain reactions hardly occur. When they do succeed, excess heat generation above the theory becomes observed.

Figure 8: Dependence of excess heat generation on current density, reproduced by Storms[69].

Figure 9: Dependence of excess heat generation on ^4He production, reproduced from McKubre[26] or Hagelstein[30].

4 Influence of dislocation in Fleischmann-Pons effect

Miles[23, 31] demonstrated that the excess heat generation in the Fleischmann-Pons effect exhibits strong manufacturer dependence. This is also considered to be due to the influence of dislocations. Specifically, manufacturing processes such as rolling and heat treatment differ by manufacturer, resulting in significantly varying dislocation densities. Table 1 summarizes typical dislocation densities in general metals under various treatments such as cold working and annealing. While thermodynamically stable metals exhibit the densities of $10^8 - 10^{11}/\text{m}^2$, cold working increases them by approximately five orders of magnitude to $10^{14} - 10^{16}/\text{m}^2$. Indeed, the dislocation density of cold-worked palladium was increased to $10^{16}/\text{m}^2$ [81]. Miles[23, 31] reported manufacturer dependence in excess heat generation, which ranged from 0 to 15 MJ/cc. Table 2 summarizes the excess heat generation density calculated from Miles[23]. Palladium supplied from Johnson Matthey plc had the best performance, and that of NRL the second best.

Table 1: Typical dislocation densities of general metals under various treatments[78-80].

Treatment	Dislocation density ($/\text{m}^2$)
Well-annealed (stable state)	$10^8 - 10^{11}$
Cold-worked	$10^{14} - 10^{16}$
Annealed	$10^{11} - 10^{13}$

Table 2: Excess heat generation densities, calculated from Miles[23].

Cathode model	d (mm)	V (cc)	Excess heat (kJ)	Heat density (MJ/cc)	Year	Days
Johnson Matthey Pd	6.35	0.36	210	0.583	1989	26
Johnson Matthey Pd	6.35	0.36	220	0.611	1989	26
Johnson Matthey Pd	6.35	0.36	300	0.833	1989	38
Johnson Matthey Pd	6.35	0.36	1400	3.889	1990	83
Johnson Matthey Pd	1	0.02	290	14.5	1992	66
NRL PdB (0.75%)	6	0.57	950	1.667	1994	137

When the dislocation density is denoted as ρ ($/\text{m}^2$), the lattice constant as $a = 3.8907 \text{ \AA}$ and the average atomic displacement of dislocation as $n \sim 1$, then the excess heat capacity density C_H of the palladium cathode is given by

$$C_H \simeq \left(\frac{n\rho}{a}\right) \cdot 23.8 \text{ (MeV/m}^3\text{)} = 9.80 \times 10^{-9} \cdot \rho \text{ (J/cc)}, \quad (6)$$

where the possible total excess heat Q and the palladium volume V have the relation $Q = C_H V$. At the maximum heat capacity of 14.5 MJ/cc shown in Table 2, ρ is estimated to be

$1.55 \times 10^{15}/\text{m}^2$. It is quite persuasive that the value falls within the dislocation density range achieved by cold working.

High excess heat generation requires the palladium cathode to be crack-free[68, 69]. Since cracks result from dislocation growth, cracks decrease excess heat generation due to the largest dislocation loss. Additionally, as dislocations are annihilated in palladium during hydrogen absorption or heating[82, 83], excess heat in metal nanoparticles is generated by heating.

To summarize, the conditions for the reproducibility of dislocation-annihilation fusion are as follows:

- Dislocation density of palladium: $\rho > 10^{14}/\text{m}^2$
- Deuterium-loading ratio: $(D/Pd) > 0.85$
- Current density of electrolysis: $I/A > 0.1\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$
- Crack free

As these values mean the thresholds of the fusion, they are different from Lawson criterion in thermonuclear fusion to get the same output power as the input. They have been primarily elucidated by McKubre and Storms. The lower limit of the dislocation density is set as that for cold working. Increasing these values, excess heat is increasingly generated. However, there might be an optimal current density for the best energy gain. Storms pointed out the importance of keeping the current density low during the deuterium-loading process before excess heat generation[69], presumably to prevent dislocation annihilation.

Cold fusion via palladium-deuterium codeposition was developed by Szapak[84, 85]. Palladium-deuterium codeposits were formed by electroplating, generating excess heat under higher current density than the codeposition. Although the dislocation density in electroplated films has not been extensively investigated, it is estimated to be comparable to that in cold-worked metals ranging from 10^{14} to $10^{16}/\text{m}^2$. For instance, dislocation densities ranging from 3.2×10^{14} to $8.6 \times 10^{14}/\text{m}^2$ have been reported for electroplated copper[86]. Generally, dislocation density can be increased by plating under non-equilibrium conditions, such as by raising the metal ion concentration in the plating bath or increasing the plating current density. However, an optimal value of current density can exist due to the trade-off between dislocation generation and annihilation .

Electrolysis methods for cold fusion reactors have the following disadvantages:

- Non-negligible large heat is dissipated from a cathode because water has a large heat capacity.
- To maintain the liquid state, the cathode temperature cannot be raised significantly above 100°C , limiting the extraction efficiency as a heat source.
- Since atomic elements except hydrogen come into contact with metals, nuclear reactions become complex to cause various nuclear transmutations, resulting in troublesome disposal issues.

Therefore, for practical applications of cold fusion, gas-phase methods to load hydrogen are more desirable.

5 H-H fusion induced by dislocation annihilation in Pd-H systems

When H-H fusion induced by dislocation annihilation is possible in the palladium-protium(hydrogen) system, the reactions are as follows:

$$p^+ + p^+ \longrightarrow d^+ + e^+ (E_p) + \nu_e (E_\nu), \quad \text{where } E_p + E_\nu \simeq 1.442 \text{ MeV} \quad (7a)$$

$$e^+(E'_p) + e^- \longrightarrow \gamma (E'_p + 0.511 \text{ MeV}) + \gamma (0.511 \text{ MeV}), \quad \text{where } E_p \geq E'_p \quad (7b)$$

In thermonuclear fusion, reaction (7a) is impossible by collisions due to the extremely low reaction cross section via 'weak' (leptonic) interaction. However, the feasibility of H-H fusion exists in palladium-protium systems. If reaction (7a) is possible, the energy distributions of positrons N_p and electron neutrinos N_ν can be approximated by $N_p(x) = 12x(1-x)^2$ and $N_\nu(x) = 12x^2(1-x)$, respectively[87]. Here, x is the energy normalized at the maximum energy, and the distributions are normalized such that their integrals from 0 to 1 sum to 1. Here, the peak positions for positrons and neutrinos are 1/3 and 2/3, respectively, and the average energies are 2/5 and 3/5, respectively. Therefore, 0.865 MeV is lost as the average neutrino energy, and the maximum energy convertible to heat via H-H fusion is $1.442 \times 0.4 + 0.511 \times 2 = 1.599$ MeV. This value is only 6.7% of the 23.8 MeV energy value generated by D-D fusion induced by dislocation annihilation. Additionally, gamma rays with peaks around 0.511 MeV and 1.088 MeV are also expected to be observed.

Possible D-H fusion reactions by dislocation annihilation are as follows:

$$d^+ + p^+ \longrightarrow {}^3\text{He}^{2+}, \quad \text{where } Q = 5.493 \text{ MeV} \quad (8a)$$

$$d^+ + p^+ \longrightarrow t^+ + e^+ (E_p) + \nu_e (E_\nu), \quad \text{where } E_p + E_\nu \simeq 4.453 \text{ MeV} \quad (8b)$$

$$e^+(E'_p) + e^- \longrightarrow \gamma (E'_p + 0.511 \text{ MeV}) + \gamma (0.511 \text{ MeV}), \quad \text{where } E_p \geq E'_p \quad (8c)$$

Because reaction (8b) to produce tritium is thermally less stable and has smaller reaction cross section due to leptonic interaction, reaction (8a) to produce ${}^3\text{He}^{2+}$ is considered to be selected.

Yamaguchi[88-90] confirmed excess heat generation in the palladium-protium system. Although he also detected D₂, he attributed it to experimental contamination. However, there existed the possibility of H-H fusion. His experiment was insufficient as he did not measure gamma rays. Furthermore, while the heat generation is expected to be 6.7% for the palladium-deuterium system, he reported the heat generation of Pd-H systems as approximately half that of Pd-D systems[90], which is about seven times larger than the predicted value. This suggests the primary reaction might be a neutron chain reaction[61] rather than H-H fusion by dislocation annihilation. In the case of the neutron chain reaction, experimental excess heat generation of about half that of Pd-D systems would be consistent with the model.

On the other hand, Arata[91, 92] and McKubre[74] concluded that no excess heat is generated in the electrolysis of H₂O with palladium cathodes. However, since the excess heat could be hidden within the measurement noise at 6.7% output of the Pd-D₂O system, a complete negation is impossible. In future, more careful experiments should be done for the clarification.

6 Reevaluation of Paneth

Sixty years before Fleischmann and Pons[1], Paneth *et al.*[93, 94] reported nuclear transmutation from hydrogen to helium in 1926, but retracted it the next year[95, 96]. Their discovery and retraction gained again notoriety when Dickman[97] cited it as an important negative evidence against cold fusion on April 27, 1989 — just one month after the Fleischmann-Pons historic announcement. Given the significance and innovation of their work, I do reevaluate it. At first, it should be noted that neither hydrogen nor helium isotopes had been discovered at that time since the concept of isotopes was proposed by Soddy[98] and two neon isotopes were discovered by Thomson[99] in 1913. Deuterium was discovered by Urey[100] in 1931. The existence of ³He and tritium was confirmed by Oliphant[65] and Rutherford[101] in 1934, and they were isolated by Alvarez[102] in 1939. Therefore, since they conducted experiments before the 1931 discovery of deuterium, they must have experimented using light hydrogen (protium) containing deuterium at its natural abundance ratio of 1.15×10^{-4} .

It is also important to understand common scientific knowledge at that time. 1920s was the scientific golden period when quantum mechanics was fully established, with matrix mechanics being published by Heisenberg[103] in 1925 and the wave equation being published by Schrödinger[104] in 1926. Furthermore, while the prototype of the modern atomic nucleus model was proposed by Rutherford[105, 106] in 1911 and the concept of a neutron was proposed by Rutherford[107] in 1920, the neutron remained an unconfirmed entity. Paneth *et al.* were tackling atomic transmutation while the atomic structure itself remained uncertain. In 1932, the neutron was experimentally confirmed by Chadwick[108], and in 1932, Heisenberg[109] established the correct atomic nucleus model composed of protons and neutrons. Therefore, a clear information gap exists between Paneth in 1926 and us at the present. However, it should be noted that German science was the greatest in the world, winning half of all Nobel Prizes in physics and chemistry before World War II. Their experimental results should not be dismissed lightly.

As mentioned above, Paneth conducted his experiments using ordinary light hydrogen (protium). D-D fusion by dislocation annihilation can be neglected, because the probability of double deuterium atoms in one site becomes extremely low. As primary reaction into helium necessarily involves at least one protium atom, the possible reactions are as follows:

The H-H-H fusion (9b) involves leptonic interactions, resulting in an extremely small reaction

cross section. However, it is a thermally more stable pathway than the D-H fusion (9a). Nevertheless, if the reaction probability of H-H-H fusion is low, the protium nucleus might escape to the tetrahedral site before the reaction completes. As mentioned in the previous section, it is not obvious that H-H fusion by dislocation annihilation is possible.

Summarizing the researches by Paneth *et al.*[93, 94]:

- Initially, helium detection was succeeded by passing hydrogen through a red-hot palladium capillary tube. From the following results, this first helium is considered not to be made from hydrogen but to be penetrated from glass. Thus, the experiments began with error and immediately became true.
- To produce helium more efficiently, sponge palladium, palladium black and palladinized asbestos were used. From a modern perspective, these materials are nanoparticles, which have the largest specific surface area to promote hydrogen absorption for cold fusion.
- When hydrogen was absorbed at high temperatures, little or no helium was produced. This is reasonable that the (H/Pd) loading decreases at high temperatures, as shown in Figure3, resulting in less or no excess heat generation. This is the main reason why the first detection of helium was a mistake.
- The palladium activity to produce helium gradually decreased and became lost in repeated experiments. The activity could be refreshed by heating in hydrogen, oxygen, the mixed gases or vacuum. This can be interpreted as dislocations were consumed for fusion during experiments, and edge dislocations were reintroduced during cooling after heating due to thermal stresses occurring between the surface and interior. Therefore, it is also expected that the dislocation will increase due to rapid cooling by the flow of an inert gas such as nitrogen.
- During about 20 experiments with palladinized asbestos, the highest activity of helium production gradually decreased and vanished at last. Although recovery was possible with the aforementioned heat treatment, the effect was limited and did not achieve full recovery. As the palladium in palladinized asbestos was formed by electroless plating, the crystallinity could be deteriorated to an amorphous state and the extremely highest dislocation density near the theoretical limit was possible. This can be interpreted as the highest activity of palladinized asbestos was due to this high dislocation density, which could not be fully recovered by heat treatment. Since dislocations originate from the deteriorated crystallinity, they should be removed by sufficiently slow cooling after heat treatment.

These qualitative behaviors are quite reasonable from the perspective of my model. However, Paneth retracted the transmutation of hydrogen into helium by palladium, because he noticed helium penetration through glass tubes from the air and initial helium absorption in the asbestos[95, 96]. Initially, he retracted only the results concerning the palladinized asbestos, maintaining that the experimental data for sponge palladium and palladium black remained

valid. However, he ultimately retracted the all results, citing the possibility of "unknown" errors. This was not a complete denial but a passive retraction. Based on current knowledge, it seems entirely possible that they succeeded in the transmutation of hydrogen into helium.

It is possible to estimate their helium yield using my model. This time, we consider only H-D fusion to produce ${}^3\text{He}$. H-H-H fusion is excluded as it remains unconfirmed. Given palladium mass M (kg), density $\rho_M = 12.02 \text{ g/cc} = 1.202 \times 10^4 \text{ kg/m}^3$, dislocation density ρ (/m²), the atomic displacement per dislocation $n \sim 1$ atom, and the palladium lattice constant $a \simeq 4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}$, the number of fusion sites N_F is given by

$$N_F \simeq \left(\frac{M}{\rho_M} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{n\rho}{a} \right). \quad (10)$$

The probability of overlapping of H and D atoms at an octahedral site is $2(D/Pd)(H/Pd) = 2.3 \times 10^{-4} \cdot (H/Pd)^2$. Furthermore, the fusion success probability is given by $(H/Pd)^{12}$, which means the probability that the 12 nearest O-sites around the fusion site are completely filled for the perfect atomic-scale confinement. From the above, the number of produced ${}^3\text{He}$, N_{He3} is given by

$$N_{He3} = N_F \cdot 2.3 \times 10^{-4} \cdot \left(\frac{H}{Pd} \right)^{14} \simeq 47.84 \cdot M\rho \left(\frac{H}{Pd} \right)^{14}. \quad (11)$$

Using Avogadro's number N_A , the ${}^3\text{He}$ volume, V_{He3} (cc) at the standard state is given by

$$V_{He3} = N_{He3} \cdot \left(\frac{22.4 \times 10^3}{N_A} \right) \simeq 1.779 \times 10^{-18} M\rho \left(\frac{H}{Pd} \right)^{14}. \quad (12)$$

Here, the standard state for a gas is defined as the condition at 0 °C under 0.1 MPa pressure. In contrast, during the 1920s, the temperature was not strictly defined and referred to room temperature, and the pressure was 1 atm = 0.101325 MPa[110]. Therefore, while the value of gas volume from the 1920s is nearly equal to the present value, it is considered to be approximately 5-8% larger than the present one in detail.

If deuterium is used instead of protium (H), ${}^4\text{He}$ is produced instead of ${}^3\text{He}$. Since the coefficient of 2.3×10^{-4} is eliminated, the produced ${}^4\text{He}$ volume, V_{He4} (cc) increases significantly to

$$V_{He4} \simeq 7.736 \times 10^{-15} M\rho \left(\frac{D}{Pd} \right)^{14}. \quad (13)$$

Paneth's paper[93] provides little description of sample weights, stating only that 10^{-6} cc of helium was obtained from 1 g of 50% palladinized asbestos. It also notes that helium yield from sponge palladium or palladium black ranged from the detection limit of 10^{-9} cc to 10^{-8} cc. Here, I evaluate the ${}^3\text{He}$ from my model. For palladium sample like palladium black, assume sample weight $M = 1 \text{ g} = 10^{-3} \text{ kg}$ and dislocation density $\rho = 10^{15} \text{ /m}^2$. While this dislocation density is a typical value for cold-worked palladium, it has also been reported for palladium nanocrystals and the density exceeds 10^{18} /m^2 in some cases[111-113]. (H/Pd) loading is approximately 0.65 at room temperature and 1 atm hydrogen pressure, as shown in Figure 3.

Applying these values to equation (12), ${}^3\text{He}$ volume is calculated as $V_{\text{He3}} = 4.275 \times 10^{-9}$ cc. This surprisingly matches their experimental results. Furthermore, if 1g of 50% palladinized asbestos has a dislocation density of $\rho = 10^{18}$ /m², the calculated $V_{\text{He3}} = 2.138 \times 10^{-6}$ cc is nearly equal to their reported value of 10^{-6} cc and entirely plausible. Although Paneth's experiments were used by Dickman in 1989 as negative evidence against cold fusion, the above estimates suggest their experiment was likely correct as the earliest excellent proof for cold fusion.

7 Conclusions

To explain cold fusion in the palladium-deuterium system, known as the Fleischmann–Pons effect, I proposed a fusion model induced by dislocation annihilation. Huizenga's three miracles are resolved as follows: The macroscopic force accompanying dislocation annihilation confines multiple deuterium nuclei at an octahedral site to overcome Coulomb repulsion, enabling quasi-static fusion with the atomic-scale confinement. As a result, the reaction produces the thermally most stable nucleus, ${}^4\text{He}$, without generating tritium or ${}^3\text{He}$. Consequently, no neutron is emitted. Because ${}^4\text{He}$ is a doubly magic nucleus, the suppression of photon emission promotes conversion of the mass deficit energy into heat via internal electron conversions or phonon interactions.

Furthermore, the reaction probability and excess heat generation are derived to be proportional to $(D/Pd)^{14}$. The threshold deuterium loading ratio required for excess heat generation is calculated as $0.1^{(1/14)} \simeq 0.85$, consistent with McKubre's law. The model also explains the dependence of excess heat generation on material properties across different manufacturers and predicts a maximum heat generation density close to values estimated from dislocation density. Thus, this framework provides not only qualitative insight into observed behaviors but also quantitative estimations of cold fusion phenomena.

Finally, Paneth's experimental results from the 1920s were reevaluated. When the amount of helium predicted by my model was estimated, it showed remarkable agreement with their reported values, strongly suggesting that Paneth's experimental observations were indeed correct as the earliest excellent proof for cold fusion. Thus, it is possible that the world's first deliberate artificial atomic transmutation from hydrogen to helium was achieved by Paneth, rather than by Oliphant and Rutherford.

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